

THEORETICAL BASIS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE APPLICATION OF NEUROTECHNOLOGIES IN PEDAGOGY

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Abstract: In this article The theoretical foundations of the application of neurotechnologies in the field of pedagogy and the culture of reading, as well as the human desire for knowledge and spiritual development, are considered in this process, it is emphasized that the application of neuropedagogical technologies in education is based on factors such as an individual approach, memory and attention enhancement. Today, the application of neurotechnologies in the education system, its importance, and its place in the lives of students are revealed.

Keywords: Neuroengineering, neurotechnology, pedagogy, cognitive development, educational technologies, critical thinking, memory, interactive learning, pedagogical technology, didactics, history of development, design, component.

Introduction.

Pedagogical technology exhibits the following specific features: In particular, Pedagogical technology is considered a factor in satisfying the social need for improving and optimizing the pedagogical process. Pedagogical technology is a set of theoretical and practical knowledge related to the effective and skillful organization of the educational process of a didactic, educational nature, as a methodological discipline.

Pedagogical technology is a holistic process that reflects the general essence of the educational process. Pedagogical technology performs a guiding function, that is, it serves to develop, educate, and form a person. Pedagogical technology has the nature of an individual, and there are no single, strict, normative (standard) requirements for the use of certain technologies in the educational process.

Each teacher has the opportunity to implement a specific technological approach, taking into account the characteristics of the educational environment in which he works, the existing internal and external conditions. Pedagogical technology represents the unity of education, upbringing and personal development (maturity).

Through neuropedagogical technologies, it is possible to form the correct approach to the process of reading books and the rules of thinking in students.

This ensures that the information obtained from books is stored in the long-term memory of students, and is more deeply perceived in the process of understanding and comprehension. At the same time, neuropedagogical technologies also provide the opportunity to add visual and audio information through auxiliary means, develop associations and make the learning process more enjoyable.

The purpose of the article is to study the theoretical foundations and significance of the use of neurotechnologies in pedagogy, as well as the advantages of using neuropedagogical technologies in the development of a reading culture, and to study their impact on students' interest in reading books and intellectual development. On this basis, the following tasks are set.

Thus, this article is aimed at highlighting the theoretical and practical foundations of the use of neurotechnologies in pedagogy, interest in reading and information processing, as well as the theoretical foundations and significance of neurotechnologies.

Advantages of neurotechnologies in the pedagogical process. Neurotechnologies are approaches based on taking into account the cognitive and neurophysiological characteristics of the human brain in the educational process. Neuropedagogical methods provide such advantages as taking into account individuality in the learning process, using visual and audio tools, enhancing attention and memory, and making the learning process enjoyable and interesting.

These approaches are also very important in developing a reading culture, because they create the opportunity to arouse interest in books in students, better understand the content of the book, and store it in long-term memory.

Theoretical foundations of developing a reading culture through neurotechnologies in pedagogy. Neuropedagogical approaches are aimed at taking into account the personal cognitive characteristics of students in developing a reading culture. This develops students' ability to concentrate, retain information in memory, and think. As Vygotsky's theory emphasizes, the development of a person should be carried out in accordance with his zone of proximal development (Vygotsky, 1982). On this basis, neuropedagogical technologies can individualize the learning process and adapt it to the developmental needs of the student.

Increasing interest in books through the use of visual and audio aids. The use of visual and audio aids in the formation of a reading culture arouses interest in books in students and helps them better understand the text. Modern

neuropedagogical technologies make the process of receiving information through various visual and audio aids enjoyable and interesting.

To more fully understand the plot or concepts in the book, videos or pictures can be added. Through these aids, students can arouse interest in the content of the book and perceive the reading process more easily.

Audiobooks provide significant assistance in the perception of text, especially for students who have difficulty perceiving visual information. Through audio books, students can hear the book by ear, which helps them better understand and retain the text in memory.

A brief visual and audio presentation of the content of the work is a good way for students to understand the main ideas of the book and arouse interest. For example, short videos or animations that directly depict the main characters or important events of the book can be used.

Cognitive exercises that help strengthen memory and concentration. Cognitive exercises are important for strengthening memory and attention. During the reading process, these exercises provide students with long-term concentration and meaningful reading, helping to retain the text in memory for a long time.

Special exercises are recommended to teach concentration when reading text. For example, the “mental dot” exercise (concentrating the thought on one point) or taking short breaks after each section helps to restore students’ attention.

Short-term memorization exercises aimed at quickly memorizing information from the book strengthen students’ memory. To do this, students are advised to repeat important ideas from the work, rewrite the main points, or create visual diagrams.

When memorizing text, students learn to process meaning and retain it in their memory through associations related to concepts. For example, relating information to their own lives or visualizing an event as a specific scenario helps to strengthen memory.

Use of e-books and interactive reading platforms. Modern e-books and interactive reading platforms are of great importance in increasing students’ interest in reading books and forming a reading culture. E-books and interactive platforms help make the process of reading books lively and effective.

E-books allow students to read books at any time and anywhere. This helps them develop the habit of reading books. At the same time, e-books can contain

bright illustrations, useful additions and interactive elements, which increases students' interest.

Conclusion.

Neuropedagogical technologies are of great importance in the development of information literacy, and their effectiveness is clearly manifested in the formation of students' abilities to perceive, analyze and correctly process information in the educational process. These technologies allow students to correctly understand information and critically think, help improve their knowledge and skills.

The use of neuropedagogical technologies has a positive effect on the general level of knowledge and cognitive skills of students. They make the process of acquiring knowledge more effective for students by developing skills such as information security, critical thinking, concentration and memory. This helps to prepare them as knowledgeable and responsible individuals who meet the requirements of modern society.

Recommendations for the widespread use of neuropedagogical technologies in education. The widespread use of neuropedagogical technologies in the educational process is important for the development of information literacy of students. It is recommended to individualize the learning process, form a culture of information security and widely implement cognitive exercises in educational institutions using neuropedagogical methods. This approach serves to improve students' attitude to information and form them as knowledgeable, thinking individuals.

As a result of scientific research conducted in the field of neuropedagogy and neuropsychology, the study of pedagogical processes from the perspective of neurological changes occurring in the human brain, that is, the synergism of neurology with pedagogy - neuropedagogy emerged as a separate discipline in 1997 and is further formed in the general field of knowledge related to the educational process of the individual, subject, and personality.

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